

RURAL CREDIT AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT

Dr. P. Sujatha

Associate Professor of economics, GDC Kharitabad, Hyderabad

Corresponding Author- **Dr. P. Sujatha**

Email- sujathap004@gmail.com

Abstract

Agriculture credit plays a crucial role in shaping agricultural economy of any country. Agriculture credit helps the farmers to commercialise their farming. As the small and the marginal farmers produce only for their subsistence, they fail to generate sufficient surplus to reinvest on their lands, to increase their produce, make additional income and improve their standard of living. So agriculture credit plays an important role in rural development.

Rural development is the process of improving the quality of life, and economic well being of people living in rural areas, often relatively isolated and sparsely populated areas. Traditionally rural development means exploitation of land intensive natural resources, such as agriculture and forestry. However changes in global networks and increased urbanisation have changed the character of rural areas like rural tourism, niche manufacturers and recreation have replaced the dominant economic drivers

This study will highlight about the different sources of credit available in rural areas, and its importance. It will also study about the effect on overall development of rural economy. The study suggests that by accelerating agricultural credit prosperity can be achieved, which in turn leads to growth in economy. It will also study about the other activities (education, enterprises, and infrastructure) which help in rural development. With rapid technological adoption and the need to improve farming operations, role of credit in agriculture has become more crucial. Studies have also established that credit market in developing countries infuse growth in the economic system in several ways.

Introduction

With the rapid technological adoption and the need to improve farming operation, role of credit in agricultural has become more crucial. Various studies have proved that agriculture credit and development in agriculture credit and development in agriculture sector is positive. Empirical studies have established that credit market in developing countries infuses growth in the economic in several ways.

Role of agriculture credit in rural economy is not only limited to agriculture growth, but helps in improvement of standards of living, health, food consumption, education, etc. Recognizing, the importance of agriculture credit, Indian policymakers have time and again introduced several measures for easy access of agricultural credit to farm households. So it is right that over the period of time discussion on rural credit has evolved to incorporate various dimensions like accessibility, productivity and disparity in credit distribution. Credit is a critical facilitator that enables adoption of technology, and higher input use in agriculture as well as an effective means of rural development. Credit is a critical facilitator that enables adoption of technology, and higher input use in agriculture as well as an effective means of rural development. Various agencies, including commercial bank, regional rural bank (RRBs), co-operatives, small finance banks (SFBs), NBFCs, micro-finance institutions (MFIs) and indigenous bankers together form the rural credit delivery system in India.

Since independence government of India (GoI), RBI and other financial institutions are trying to minimise the share of non-institutional credit in agriculture. Over the years, multiple committees have been formed to recommend ways to increase the institutional credit in agriculture and rural areas. These include the R. V. Gupta Committee on Agricultural Credit through Commercial Banks, Vikhe Patil Committee on Cooperatives, V.S. Vyas Advisory Committee on Flow of Credit to Agriculture, and A. Vaidynathan Task Force on Revival of Co-operative Credit Institutions. The GoI has accepted most of the recommendations and brought reforms suggested by these committees.

In this direction several initiatives have been taken time to time, e.g., accepting Rural Credit Survey Committee Report (1954), nationalisation of the commercial banks in 1969 and 1980, establishment of RRBs (1975), establishment of National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) (1982), etc. Apart from institutional changes, GoI, RBI and NABARD have brought multiple schemes to increase credit penetration in agriculture like establishment of Lead Bank Scheme, provision of priority sector lending, self-help group – bank linkage programme (SHG-BLP), lending to joint liability group, kisan credit card scheme, Rural Infrastructure Development Fund (RIDF), etc. to increase credit penetration in rural areas.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study about the different sources of rural credit.
2. To discuss about the role of NABARD in rural development

Methodology:

This study is based on secondary data. Data is collected from various journals, articles, NABARD reports and from internet.

What is Rural Credit

Agriculture is the primary source of income for people living in India's rural areas. Farmers and peasants have to invest a significant amount of funds each year to guarantee a healthy crop. As a result, they frequently borrow money from moneylenders and financial institutions to meet their basic requirements before harvest season so they can make money by selling their crops. Thus, **Agricultural Rural Credit** refers to any loan taken for agricultural reasons or small home enterprises in India's rural regions.

Purpose of credit requirement

The rural economy's growth is primarily dependent on capital infusions from time to time to achieve better productivity in agriculture and non-agriculture sectors. Farmers borrow from various sources to meet their initial investment in seeds, fertilisers, tools, and other family costs such as marriage, funerals, religious rituals, and so on, because the time gap between crop sowing and realisation of income after production is quite long.

Moneylenders and merchants abused small and marginal farmers and landless labourers during the freedom period by lending them at high interest rates and manipulating their accounts to keep them in debt. After 1969, India implemented social banking and a multiagency strategy to properly satisfy the requirements of Agricultural Rural Credit.

Rural areas frequently suffer from poor income, which leads to a low rate of savings. Farmers have a tough time increasing their productivity by spending on farmland. Credit in many ways helps farmers to commercialize their farming. Even though small and marginal farmers produce only for subsistence, they do not generate enough surpluses to reinvest in their lands, resulting in land deterioration. Agriculture has always been dependent on the weather. Farmers suffer the most when there is no rainfall or harvest failure. Crop insurance and agricultural rural credit are thus critical in saving them from such disasters.

Need for Rural Credit

There are two angles through which the credit needs of the farmers can be examined. These are:

- On the Basis of Time
- On the Basis of Purpose

1. On the Basis of Time: Based on time, there are three categories under which the credit needs can be classified:

- **Short-term Credit:** The credit taken by the farmers for a period of less than 15 months in order to meet their short-term needs is known as Short-term Credit. The purpose of short-term credit is to purchase seeds, pay wages to the hired workers, buy fertilisers, etc. The repayment of such credit can be made out of the farmer's current income.
- **Medium-term Credit:** The credit taken by the farmers for a medium period between 15 months and 5 years is known as Medium-term Credit. The purpose of medium-term credit is for productive activities (purchase of agricultural implements, cattle, etc.) and unproductive activities (expense on social functions, marriage, etc.).
- **Long-term Credit:** The credit taken by the farmers for a long period of more than 5 years, which can even extend to 15 to 20 years in order to meet long-term needs is known as Long-term Credit. The repayment of such loans is done over a long time period. The purpose of Long-term Credit is to dig tubewell, repay old debts, purchase of large agricultural implements, etc.

2. On the Basis of Purpose: Based on purpose, there are two categories under which the credit needs can be classified:

- **Productive Loans:** The loans which help the farmers raise agricultural productivity and production are known as Productive Loans. **For example**, loans taken by the farmers to buy seeds, farm implements, fertilizers, or to make permanent improvements on their land.
- **Unproductive Loans:** The loans which do not help the farmers raise agricultural productivity and production are known as Unproductive Loans. **For example**, loans taken for marriage, religious functions, social functions, etc.

Sources of Rural Credit in India

The two sources of rural credit from which the farmers can raise loans are as follows:

Non-institutional Sources (Informal):

It constitutes of cash lenders, free agents, landlords, relatives, and friends. Historically, non-institutional sources satisfied or fulfilled the majority of farmers' credit requirements due to their simpler loan procedures and willingness to give even for unproductive purposes. However, due to restricted resources, they were unable to satisfy their medium and long-term needs/requirements. These sources accounted for roughly 93% of the full credit score requirement of the agricultural people in 1950-51 and at present account for 34% of the most effective credit score requirement. They used to take advantage of small and marginal farmers by asking high rates of interest and manipulating accounts to keep them in debt.

The major non-institutional sources of rural credit are:

1. **Moneylenders:** Moneylenders have long been a source of credit for many agricultural households in India's rural credit environment. However, they exploit peasants through high rates of interest and even manipulate their accounts to keep them in debt.
2. **Traders and Commission Agents:** Traders and commission agents give loans to agriculturists for productive reasons before crop maturity and then compel farmers to sell their harvests at very low rates to them while charging a high fee. This form of loan is typically used for cash crops.
3. **Relatives:** In times of crisis, cultivators frequently borrow funds from their own relatives, either in cash or in kind. These are informal debts that have no interest and are usually repaid after harvest.
4. **Rich Landlords:** In India, small and marginal cultivators and tenants are also accepting loans from landowners to satisfy their financial requirements. This source has been following all of the bad practices of moneylenders, merchants, and so on. Landless workers are sometimes forced to work as bonded laborers.

2. Institutional Sources (Formal):

It is mainly composed of the government, cooperative societies, rural municipal financial institutions, industrial financial institutions, and other entities. It accounted for the most efficient 7% of the general credit score requirement at the start of the main five years plan (in 1950-51), but it is now due for approximately 66%. Some of the Institutional sources of rural credit are as follows:

1. **Co-operative Credit:** The main goal of co-operatives is to free Indian peasants from the clutches of moneylenders and provide them with credit at low interest rates. This is the most cost-effective and essential source of rural financing. It was established with the goal of facilitating small and medium-sized farmers' complete financing requirements.
2. **Land Development Banks:** These institutions lend money to farmers in exchange for a lien on their property. Loans are available for permanent property improvement, the purchase of farming tools, and the repayment of past obligations.
3. **Commercial Bank Credit:** Commercial banks initially played a minor part in promoting rural credit. However, after nationalization in 1969, they extended their rural branches and began directly financing farmers.
4. **Regional Rural Banks:** India is an agriculturally oriented nation with a large population engaged in the agricultural sector. Thus, in order to utilize this sector and connect Indian farmers with banks in order to facilitate financial transactions, the Government of India established

Regional Rural Banks. (RRB). Regional rural banks in India play a key role in providing banking facilities to farmers living in remote areas.

5. National Bank for Agricultural and Rural Development

(NABARD): National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) is the Apex Bank which has to coordinate the functioning of various financial institutions that are working for the expansion of rural credit. The basic objective of NABARD is to promote the health and strength of credit institutions including commercial banks, cooperatives, and regional rural banks. It also provides assistance to the non-farm sectors for the promotion of integrated rural development and prosperity of backward rural areas.

6. Self-Help Group (SHG) Bank Linkages Programme for Micro Finance:

The primary emphasis of SHGs is on the rural poor, who lack long-term access to the formal banking system. Therefore, the targeted customers of SHGs include small and marginal farms, agricultural and nonagricultural workers, artisans, and so on. SHGs encourage thrift in small portions by asking for a minimal contribution from each member. Credit is granted to needy members at fair interest rates, to be returned in small instalments from the pooled funds.

7. The Government- The Government provides short and long term goals to farmers if there is an emergency like famine and flood. These type of loans are also known as Taccavo loans.

As the banking system expanded rapidly, it affected the rural farm and non-farm output, income, and employment positively. After the green revolution, farmers could use credit facilities to avail of different loans in order to meet their production needs. Besides, famines have become an event of the past with the rise in buffer stock.

Role of Rural Banking in Rural Development

Rural Development in India is the overall progress in the economic and social

conditions of Indians residing in rural areas. Rural development is possible by developing Agriculture sector and also non agriculture sector.

Need of study:

The rural economy is an agrarian economy. One of the most important activities is agriculture. About two thirds India's population depends on agriculture, but its share in GDP is constantly decreasing. As a result the productivity is not up to mark with conditions only getting worse.

Moreover the public investment is declining since 1991 coupled with lack of infrastructure, credit transport etc. therefore there is a need to focus on rural development.

Various pressing issues of village economics that hinder growth are public health and sanitation, literacy female empowerment, enforcement of law and order, land reform and availability of credit. Rural development can be improved by the implementing the following:

Credit System in Rural Areas:

Credit plays an important role in rural development. Due to lack of capital, most of farmers are still using outdated techniques which result in low production.

To increase production, a capital infusion in reference to agricultural and non- agricultural activities can be achieved by reforming credit and banking system.

The Post – independence period saw exploitation of rural poor in need of credit by the hands of moneylenders and traders loans were granted at high rate of interest rates which ultimately puts them into debt trap. NABARD was established in 1982 by RBI to stop their exploitation. NABARD has been given, powers that establish it as the apex banking body in

rural India which regulates all the credit and banking activities of rural India.

ROLE OF NABARD

Mainly there are five functions of NABARD

- Credit functions
- Development and promotional functions
- Supervisory functions
- Institutional and capacity building
- Role of training

NABARD plays its important role by:

- Framing policy and guidelines for rural finance institutions
- Providing credit facilities to issuing organization
- Preparation of potential-linked credit plans annually
- Monitoring the flow of ground level rural credit
- NABARD has been undertaking a number of developmental and promotional activities such as, to help cooperatives bank, RRBs in preparing development actions plans, helping in entering MoUs and Supervising actions plan
- It also provides financial assistance to cooperative, RRBs for established to technical monitoring, and evaluations cells.
- It also provides financial support for training institutions.
- It creates awareness among borrower on ethics of repayment through farmer's club
- Provides recommendations to RBI on opening of new branches by SCBs and RRBs.

Scope for improving rural development:

- Employment opportunities have to be increased in rural areas by improving the productivity of agriculture sector.
- Infrastructure development will remove the gaps that exist between rural and urban.
- Quality education can help us in achieving the goal of social evils.
- Women empowerment through SHGs and agri - enterprises can change the scenario of rural areas.
- Modern technology like organic farming should be incorporated to improve outputs and profits.
- Lastly it is easy access to institutional credit by improving the banking system in rural areas will pave way for rural development.

Conclusion:

NABARD has paved a way for rural development through various development activities and various investment projects taking place in rural areas. Not only that it is also concentrating on developing other sectors like small scale industries, cottage and village industries, handicrafts and allied economic activities with agriculture sector to promote prosperity of rural areas. It is successful in diverting the farmers from informal sector to

formal sector. . So it can be concluded that the banks in rural areas are playing an important role in rural development.

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